

Visible Absorption Spectra of Anthraquinones : Use of Shift Reagents in Structure Determination

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A careful analysis of the bathochromic shifts induced by the usual shift reagents on the 'last visible band' (LVB) of the visible absorption spectra of twenty-six hydroxy-anthraquinones has revealed the usefulness of these shift reagents in the allocation of the hydroxyl groups in these compounds. Empirical rules very similar to those developed with flavonoids are advanced and their utility as well as limitations discussed.

EARLIER workers have examined the uv-visible spectra of hydroxyanthraquinones¹ from the point of view of structural analysis. However, no work seems to have been done on the use of the recently developed flavonoid uv-shift reagents^{2,3} in the structural analysis of hydroxyanthraquinones, and the present paper is aimed at filling this gap. It has been found in the present work that the visible absorption spectrum of hydroxyanthraquinones, especially the band that occurs at the longest wavelength, hereinafter designated as the 'last visible band' (LVB), undergoes distinct bathochromic shifts in the presence of some of the shift reagents in a way that could permit a reasonable structural analysis. Since the hydroxyanthraquinones examined in the present work, with very few exceptions, do not contain more than three hydroxyl groups, the results are not claimed to be very general ones though it is found very useful in the structural analysis of mono- and dihydroxy-anthraquinones. The shift reagents used are sodium acetate, sodium ethoxide, aluminium chloride, with and without added hydrochloric acid, magnesium acetate and boric acid. The results are tabulated in Table 1.

Experimental

Throughout the work 95% ethanol was used as solvent.

Sodium ethoxide reagent was prepared by dissolving freshly cut sodium (2.5 g) in ethanol (100 ml). Magnesium acetate (AnalaR ; 5 g) reagent was prepared by dissolving it in ethanol (100 ml). Sodium acetate, aluminium chloride, hydrochloric acid and boric acid reagents were prepared as described earlier².

All spectra were recorded using ethanol solutions in a Perkin-Elmer 402 spectrophotometer. A stock solution of the hydroxyanthraquinone was prepared by dissolving a known weight of the compound in ethanol (25 ml) in a standard flask. The concentration was adjusted by dilution of the stock solution in the cell by addition of ethanol so that the major absorption peak had an O.D. of 0.8–1.2. All parent spectra were run in the medium scan while those after the addition of the shift reagents were run in a fast scan. The results along with the various shift increments obtained on the addition of specific reagents are given in Table 1.

The sodium ethoxide spectra were measured immediately after the addition of three drops of the reagent to the stock solution. The aluminium chloride spectra were taken immediately or after 3–4 h, as the case may be, after the addition of the reagent (6 drops) to the stock solution (2–3 ml). The magnesium acetate spectra were recorded immediately after the addition of the reagent (3 drops) to the stock solution. The magnesium acetate-hydrochloric acid spectra were recorded immediately after the addition of hydrochloric acid (3 drops) to the above solution. The sodium acetate spectra, aluminium chloride-hydrochloric acid spectra and sodium acetate-boric acid spectra were recorded as described earlier².

Results and Discussion

Use of sodium acetate and sodium ethoxide shift reagent: Hydroxyls at the α -positions of an anthraquinone, viz. nos. 1, 4, 5 and 8 (Table 1) do not ionise under the influence of a mild base like sodium acetate. Hence the last visible band (LVB) in neutral ethanol medium (λ_{EtOH}) of anthraquinones

TABLE I—UV-VISIBLE SPECTRA OF HYDROXYANTHRAQUINONES (LVB: λ_{max} IN nm)*

Sl. no.	Structure	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)	(15)
1.	1-Hydroxy-2-methyl	420	420	—	510	90	—	420	505	85	505	530	110	420	420	—
2.	1-Hydroxy-2-methoxy	420	420	—	520	100	—	420	520	100	520	520	100	420	420	—
3.	1-Hydroxy-2-methoxy-3-methyl	420	420	—	520	100	—	420	500	80	500	520	100	420	420	—
4.	1-Hydroxy-2-methoxy-methoxy-3-methyl	420	420	—	530	110	—	420	500	80	500	520	100	420	420	—
5.	1-Hydroxy-2-methoxy-methoxy	410	410	—	515	105	—	410	480	70	480	510	100	410	410	—
6.	1,4-Dihydroxy	520	520	—	610	90	—	566	566	46	566	590	70	520	520	—
7.	1,4-Dihydroxy-2-methyl	524	524	—	600	76	—	560	560	96	560	584	60	524	524	—
8.	1,4-Dihydroxy-5,8-dimethoxy-2-methyl	560	560	—	590	90	—	596	596	96	596	610	50	560	560	—
9.	1,5-Dihydroxy-6-methoxy-2-methyl	390	390	—	520	130	—	436	436	46	436	530	140	390	390	—
10.	1,8-Dihydroxy-6-methoxy-3-methyl	450	450	—	520	70	—	520	520	70	450	510	60	450	450	—
11.	1,8-Dihydroxy-6-methoxy-2-hydroxymethyl	450	450	—	525	75	—	520	520	70	450	510	60	450	450	—
12.	1,4,8-Trihydroxy-6-methoxy-3-methyl	530	530	—	600	70	—	578	578	48	578	590	60	530	530	—
13.	1,5,8-Trihydroxy-3-methyl	530	530	—	606	76	—	580	580	50	580	594	64	530	530	—
14.	1,4,5,8-Tetrahydroxy-2-methyl	562	620	58	590	28	—	630	630	68	630	606	44	562	562	—
15.	1-Methoxy-2-hydroxy	400	510	110	510	110	—	400	400	—	400	520	120	400	400	—
16.	1-Methoxy-2-hydroxy-3-methyl	385	530	145	530	145	—	385	385	—	385	530	145	385	385	—
17.	1-Methoxy-2-formyl-3-hydroxy	380	480	100	480	100	—	450	450	70	380	460	80	380	380	—
18.	1,2-Dihydroxy	440	560	130	620	180	60	510	510	70	440	570	130	440	470	30
19.	1,2-Dihydroxy-3-methyl	450	570	120	640	190	70	520	520	70	520	580	130	450	480	30
20.	1,5,6-Trihydroxy-2-methyl	460	570	110	625	165	55	530	530	70	530	610	150	460	480	20
21.	1,3-Dihydroxy-2-formyl	425	490	65	540	115	50	470	470	45	—	510	85	425	425	—
22.	1,6,8-Trihydroxy-3-hydroxymethyl	450	516	66	540	90	24	520	520	70	450	530	80	450	450	—
23.	1,2,5,8-Tetrahydroxy	530	580	50	650	120	70	600	600	70	574	640	110	530	530	—
24.	1,2,3-Trihydroxy	450	450	—	—	—	—	575	575	125	—	560	110	450	470	20
25.	1-Methoxy-2,3-dihydroxy	400	400	—	—	—	—	530	530	130	400	570	170	400	400	—
26.	1-Hydroxy-7-methyl	410	410	—	500	90	—	410	500	90	500	510	100	410	410	—

* (1) λ_{EtOH} , (2) $\lambda_{\text{EtOH/OAc}^-}$, (3) $\Delta\lambda_{\text{OAc}^-}$, (4) $\lambda_{\text{EtOH/OEt}^-}$; (5) $\Delta\lambda_{\text{OEt}^-}$, (6) $\Delta\lambda_{\text{OEt}^-} - \Delta\lambda_{\text{OAc}^-}$, (7) $\lambda_{\text{EtOH/AlCl}_3}$ (Inst.); (8) $\lambda_{\text{EtOH/AlCl}_3}$ (3 h); (9) $\Delta\lambda_{\text{AlCl}_3}$; (10) $\lambda_{\text{EtOH/AlCl}_3/\text{HCl}}$, (11) $\lambda_{\text{EtOH/Mg(OAc)}_2}$; (12) $\Delta\lambda_{\text{Mg(OAc)}_2}$; (13) $\lambda_{\text{EtOH/Mg(OAc)}_2/\text{HCl}}$; (14) $\lambda_{\text{EtOH/NaOAc/H}_2\text{BO}_3}$; (15) $\Delta\lambda_{\text{NaOAc-H}_2\text{BO}_3}$.

having hydroxyl groups in these positions remains practically the same as when measured in the presence of added sodium acetate ($\lambda_{\text{EtOH/OAc}^-}$). The bathochromic shift ($\Delta\lambda_{\text{OAc}^-}$) is zero. Sodium ethoxide is a stronger base and can ionise the α -hydroxyl group of an anthraquinone. The absorption maximum in the presence of added sodium ethoxide ($\lambda_{\text{EtOH/OEt}^-}$) is considerably shifted to longer wavelength and this bathochromic shift ($\Delta\lambda_{\text{OEt}^-}$) seems to be dependent on the structure and is approximately 70–130 nm. The relevant data are listed in Table I (sl. nos. 1–13) and illustrated in Fig. 1 for the compound sl. no. 10.

A hydroxyl group in β -position 2, 3, 6 and 7) of the anthraquinone nucleus is more acidic by virtue of its conjugation with the quinone carbonyl. Even a mild base like sodium acetate can ionise it and induce a considerable bathochromic shift ($\Delta\lambda_{\text{OAc}^-}$) of its LVB by about 50–145 nm. This can be used as a test for the presence of a β -hydroxyl group. In an anthraquinone having only one hydroxyl group at any of the four β -posi-

Fig. 1. Shift of LVB observed in 1,8-dihydroxy-6-methoxy-3-methylanthraquinone on addition of NaOAc and NaOEt.

tions, the bathochromic shift due to sodium acetate seems to be the limit. In these cases, $\Delta\lambda_{\text{OEt}^-}$ and $\Delta\lambda_{\text{OAc}^-}$ are just the same and there is no extra shift increment. This can be used as a test for detecting the presence of a lone β -hydroxyl group in an anthraquinone. However, when an α -hydroxyl is present in addition to a β -hydroxyl, a much larger

bathochromic shift of the LVB is obtained on sodium ethoxide addition than with sodium acetate and the observation of this additional bathochromic shift increment can be taken to indicate the presence of at least one α -hydroxyl group in addition to a β -hydroxyl. These cases are listed in Table 1 (sl. nos. 18–23) and the relevant points are illustrated in Figs. 2 and 3 for the compounds sl. nos. 15 and 18.

Fig. 2. Shift of LVB observed in 1-methoxy-2-hydroxyanthraquinone on addition of NaOAc and NaOEt

Fig. 3. Shift of LVB observed in 1,2-dihydroxyanthraquinone on addition of NaOAc and NaOEt.

Cynodontin (1,4,5,8-tetrahydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone) seems to be the only exception which exhibits a bathochromic shift of its LVB on the addition of sodium acetate. The LVB at 562 nm in ethanolic solution gets shifted bathochromically by 58 nm in this case. Here the four α -hydroxyl groups enter into various *p*-quinonoid resonance forms which the molecule is capable of and these resonance interactions render them free from chelation so as to behave like ordinary unchelated phenolic hydroxyls. The case of anthragallol (1,2,3-trihydroxyanthraquinone) and its 1-methyl ether is quite peculiar in that they do not show any significant visible band and hence not amenable to the alkaline shift reagent study outlined above. It is likely that the resonance delocalisation of the phenoxide ions is opposed to each other with the result that the absorption maximum does not reach the visible range which is a measure of electron delocalisation. That this conclusion is correct could be seen from the observation that anthragallol-1-methyl ether (1-methoxy-2,3-dihydroxyanthraquinone) having two vicinal β -hydroxyl groups behaves in a similar way and

anthragallol-2,3-dimethyl ether, having only one α -hydroxyl, behaves in the way expected for an α -hydroxyanthraquinone.

Use of aluminium chloride shift reagent: The EtOH spectrum of an anthraquinone having only β -hydroxyl group remains virtually unaffected on the addition of aluminium chloride since such a compound can not form an aluminium complex. The exception to this rule is provided only by damnacanthal and nor-damnacanthal (sl. nos. 17 and 21). This could be due to complexation with the β -aldehyde group and this has not been examined in the present work. In contrast to the general experience with flavonoids, anthraquinones having only one hydroxyl group and that too present in the α -position do not form such complexes immediately. In such cases, when the spectra are measured immediately, no bathochromic shift ($\Delta\lambda_{AlCl_3}$) is observed. In all the cases (sl. nos. 1–5 and 26), this feature is repeated. However, if the spectra in these cases are run 3–4 h after the addition of the shift reagent, a distinct bathochromic shift ($\Delta\lambda_{AlCl_3}$) in the order of 70–100 nm is observed. This is illustrated in Fig. 4 corresponding to compound sl. no. 1 (Table 1).

Fig. 4. Shift of LVB observed in 1-hydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone on addition of $AlCl_3$ and HCl.

Compounds containing larger number of hydroxyl groups present points of interest. There is no time lag in these cases and the shift is immediate. Compounds having 1,4- and 1,2-dihydroxy groups (with no more hydroxyls in the same ring) reveal unmistakable fine structures in the region 520–600 nm. The $\Delta\lambda_{AlCl_3}$ in these cases is about 40–70 nm and the LVB is also intensified. 1,8-Dihydroxy compounds also exhibit this bathochromic shift of the LVB and the complex formed in all these cases remain reasonably stable. These features are illustrated in Fig. 5 corresponding to compound sl. no. 6 (Table 1). The acid-stability of these complexes seems to be related to the structure and presents some points of interest. In the cases of 1,4- and 1,5-dihydroxyanthraquinones, since the two hydroxyls can independently form complex with the two quinone carbonyls, the complexes seem to be quite stable and there is no change (shift) in their LVB on acid addition. Compounds sl. nos. 6 and 7 (Table 1) illustrate this feature. In the case

Fig. 5. Shift of LVB observed in 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone on addition of $AlCl_3$ and HCl .

of 1,8-dihydroxy compounds, where either of the two hydroxyls can form complex with the same quinone carbonyl, the complex formed decomposes on addition of acid and the spectrum run after acid addition practically resembles the parent spectrum of the compound run in ethanol. It seems that, since the quinone carbonyl forms complexes with either of the hydroxyl groups, there is stable complex formation with neither. In the case of 1,2-dihydroxy groups, the decomposition of the complex seems to depend on other structural features. Thus with alizarin (1,2-dihydroxyanthraquinone), the decomposition of the complex is quick, while in the case of quinalizarin (1,2,4-trihydroxyanthraquinone) and 3-methylalizarin, the decomposition is only partial. These points are listed in Table 1.

Use of magnesium acetate shift reagent : The use of magnesium acetate as shift reagent, specially in conjunction with the aluminium chloride reagent, is of considerable utility in the allocation of the hydroxyl group positions in anthraquinones. The shift induced by this complexing agent is very often more pronounced than with aluminium chloride and confirms the conclusions obtained with the latter. Though there is shift obtained with this reagent when both α - and β -hydroxyls are present, the shift with the former is more pronounced than there is an unmistakable intensity increase of the

LVB. In all the cases that have been studied so far, the complex is found to be destroyed on addition of hydrochloric acid and the parent spectrum is obtained. The relevant data are illustrated in Table 1.

Use of sodium acetate-boric acid shift reagent : Compounds having only α -hydroxyl or β -hydroxyl do not reveal any bathochromic shift on the addition of this reagent. However, when the molecule contains an *ortho*-dihydroxy unit, a borate complex seems to be produced though the effect is not well-pronounced. Very often in these cases, a slight bathochromic shift of 20–30 nm is observed and also attended with a distinct intensity increase. The data with such cases as alizarin, 3-methylalizarin, morindone ((1,5,6-trihydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone) and quinalizarin (1,2,5,8-tetrahydroxyanthraquinone) are listed in Table 1 (sl. nos. 18, 19, 20 and 23).

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